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EXPLORATION OF INNOVATION SKILLS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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Abstract: In the present scenario, in every field, there is a throat-cut competition. Survive in this scenario, innovative ideas, imagination, ground-breaking research, transformation, disruptive changes, etc. are must in every field. Thinking out of the box is no more “out of the box” in today's competitive world, we need a certain set of skills that enhance the proficiency of a person, which is innovation skills. It is the group of skills which helps individual to become innovative in what they do, as this is the combination of critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration. Without education, a person is useless, same without innovation skills education is nothing. In this paper, innovative skills are explored in B.Ed. First-year pupil teachers and their relationship with their academic achievement. The Descriptive Survey method is used to collect the data through a five-rating scale of innovative skills tool and Product Moment Coefficient of correlation is used to see the relationship of innovative skills with their academic achievement. The Random Cluster Sampling Technique is used for a sample of 45 pupil teachers from B.Ed. of Ghaziabad institute affiliated under CCS University. Exploration of innovative skills is more important for development in every field and its relationship with academic achievement is positive. As innovation skills are necessary for development in every field, it will help to modify the syllabus according to skills, for teachers to understand the students, and policymakers also to prepare policies in different areas. Kothari Commission (1964-66) also focused on innovation, as innovation skills are the need for future growth and rely on the education of people. Innovation skills are the critical factor to achieve the aims of the Atal Innovation Mission at NITI Aayog which are to create an environment of scientific temperament, innovation, creativity among Indian students.

Keywords: Innovation skills, critical thinking skills, problem-solving skills, creative skills, communication skills, and collaboration skills.

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“Our future growth relies on competitiveness and innovation, skills and productivity... and these in turn rely on the education of our people.”

Introduction

Education is an illumination. Education plays a significant role in the lives of an individual by empowering with various abilities, skills, and competencies, thus paving way for enhancing the quality of life. For future economic growth, social development, and development in all areas, innovation is necessary for the present scenario. Today thought cut competition is going on and to survive, to stability and to improve innovation in different areas is required. Innovation should be based on future disruptive projections not on existing old assumptions. Future disruptive innovations are based on imagination and existing old assumptions are based on experiences. Anyone can maintain based on experiences, but for the improvement or development imagination is a must. Imagination is only the way to improvement and development. Thus, disruptive innovation is a technology in which applications affect the way of market or industry, or institution functions. There are two words agility and stability; agility will help to go ahead or to improve or development and stability will help to maintain or manage through a process. For example, if talked about 1900-1910 Radio was a remarkably interesting and useful innovation. At that time no one thought that radio with photos could come and in 1920 when T.V. was introduced everyone was surprised that a photo of the speaker can be seen. It is disruptive, a 100 % change. After CRT TV (Cathode Ray Tube, Black, and White TV) CRT TV (Colour Cathode Ray Tube, Colour TV) was introduced, and then Plasma Display Panel, then Liquid Crystal Display (LCD), then Light Emitting Diode (LED) TV then Organic Light Emitting Diode (OLED) TV. This disruption came not only on TV, but disruption came on the phone also. Now a day's maximum no. of applications has been added to the phone to make easy human life, it is called disruption. In 1996 clock and calendar were added to a phone, then in 2002 0.3-megapixel camera added then email added by Blackberry then in 2005 first Walkman phone was introduced and in 2008 smartphone came in which internet newspaper watch TV, etc. has been included. Today in a phone many applications like a clock, calendar, music, radio, movie, TV, games, calculator, email, booking, banking, shopping, web browsing, wallet, alarm, help monitoring, camera, newspaper, file manager, torch, etc. have been added to make human life easy and comfortable. It is not enough many mobile applications are prepared with android to make human life easier and more comfortable. No one can believe that up by 2030 Android software will disrupt 80 % of industries. Amazon, flip kart, Ola, Uber, Airbnb, Paytm, etc. these all is software that has changed the mode of transaction and way of business. In this way, after 20 years current skills will be obsoleted. New types of jobs will be introduced. Whatever is taught in schools in the present scenario will not be useful after 30 years as too many changes and innovations will be introduced. Several types of printer are used like scanner, printer, coloured printer, 2D printer, etc., but 3D scanner printer is the storm in printing machines. In the 3D printer, additive

manufacturing is using. In it, everything from spoons to the airplane can be scanned and in a 3D form, we can receive. Human beings also can be scanned and can receive a statue of that human being. The 3D printer is used in many fields like healthcare, manufacturing, automotive, aerospace, construction, etc. Anyone can search about Additive Manufacturing 3D printing on Google. In Dubai and in China many buildings have been prepared with the help of 3D printing. It is an innovation to save time and money. The entire world is changing rapidly. 3D printers, Farming Robots, Google driverless cars, LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology, Artificial intelligence (AI), etc. many innovations are introduced for revolution in every field.

To promote innovation government of India has set up the Atal Innovation Mission at National Institute for Transforming India (NITI) Aayog with the aim to create an environment of scientific temperament, innovation, creativity among Indian pupil teachers (Home - (National Institution for Transforming India), Government of India - NITI AAYOG, n.d.). It is a step towards a new India. In this innovative research, skills will be explored among B.Ed. Pupil teachers and relationship with academic achievement, as innovative skills are the need for future growth and rely on the education of people which will be helpful in Atal Innovation Mission also. As without education, a person is useless, same without innovation education is nothing.

For innovation, there are required for an expert in some skills. In other words, for innovation, a person should have a set of some skills as for innovation a person would have to think, would search some problems and to solve problems a person would have to communicate, collaborate and critical thinking also required. And after all this, some creative decisions must take. Thus, it can be said that for innovation a set of skills is required, and that set can be called innovative skills.

To get success in the future innovative skills are required in the student. Innovative skills are the group of skills that helps individuals to become innovative in what they do, and these are the combination of critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration.

A study found that there is a positive relationship between Problem-solving and academic achievement (Beyazsacali, 2017). Teachers play a pivotal role to inculcate different skills in pupil teachers at every level. Instructions in higher education through PBL (Problem based learning) and other methods facilitate deep approaches to learning and pupil teachers' achievements positively affected (Kärkkäinenii, 2014). In Australia, a study on VET (Vocational Educational Training) clear that Innovation is a process of some activities with innovative ideas and creativity which implication helps to culminate (John Mitchell, 2003). OECD (The organization for economic co-operation and development) also focuses on innovation in teaching and learning. For innovation right skills must develop in society and schools among pupil teachers. Critical thinking, imagination, and creativity skills are the right skills that would help in innovation (OECD, 2016). Innovation is

especially important for the stability of the political and social system. For a greater impact on the system, coordination is necessary to relate the various aspects of the innovation. Asian countries have a progressive nature of innovation and the whole education system is affected by them (Wong, 1974). Innovation has gravitation to congregate in a geographical area. In the present scenario, innovations arise and take shape quickly. In India, most innovations attempt great input of human efforts (Naik, 1974). Critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, communication, and creativity skills are the main skills to enhance the 21st century's innovative skills (Payne, 2017). AACTE (The American Association of Colleges for Teacher Education) introduced some skills like critical thinking, collaboration, communication, and technology literacy that are most important for 21st-century knowledge and skills (AACTE, 2010).

AMA (American Management Association) cleared through critical skills surveys that critical thinking, communication skills, collaboration or team building, creativity, and innovation are the most required skills for the development of good workers and these critical skills can be inculcated easily among pupil teachers (AMA, 2012). Critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, social skills, etc. are important not only for teachers, important for pupil teachers also for new millennium learners in OECD countries. According to the OECD countries like Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Finland, Ireland, Italy, Spain, Portugal, etc. cleared the different skills for 21st-century skills and competencies (Claro, 2009). Collaboration, ICT literacy, social or cultural competencies, communication, creativity, critical thinking, productivity, and problem-solving are the main 21st-century competencies. Mostly competencies like critical thinking and problem solving are always associated with academic achievement (Roblin, 2012).

Innovative Skills

There are many types of skills such as life skills, soft skills, etc. like this innovative skill is also for the empowerment of the pupil teachers with critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration. Thus, in this research, innovative skills are the group of some skills which are Critical Thinking, Problem Solving, Creativity, Communication, and collaboration.

Critical Thinking

According to Lyutykh (2009), critical thinking is the right way to think. Mason, 2008 said that it is a special skill that helps to evaluate the presented reasons especially. Howell and Kemp (2005) believe that it is an individual decision or thinking or responsibility to deal with daily life. Bullen (1998) states that it is believed whatever we do. Facion and Facion (1994) states that inductive and deductive reasoning, analysis, and evaluation are included

in critical thinking. Thus, there are many statements about critical thinking.

Critical thinking is that skill which helps an individual person to think positively in daily life situation and achieve successes. It is must go ahead. For critical thinking, perception, assumptions, emotions, logic, and implications, and consequences are required. Without perception, assumptions, emotions, logic and implications, and consequences we cannot go ahead or cannot get success. We can say that to think positively in daily life and to get success critical thinking is required.

Critical thinking is given by Socrates and recorded by his pupil Plato. He focused on perception as without it we cannot analyse the basic concepts. He asked many questions which known the best way of critical thinking strategy today. Through questioning, he made the people curious to know the need of thinking for clarity and logical consistency. He helped the people to reveal their irrational thinking or lack of reliable knowledge so that they start to think critically. Socrates's pupil Plato gave the name Critical Thinking to the teaching of Socrates.

Problem-Solving

The higher order of thinking like Visualization, abstraction, comprehension, manipulation, association, reasoning, analysis, synthesis, generalization, etc. are problem-solving skills. Each wanting to be managed and coordinated (Lester, 1985).

It can be said that problem solving is a process in which a person first identifies the problems on the base of thinking level, then explain and present that how to be solved and after this planned to solve the problem and collected the information. According to prioritize resources would be selected and used. Then follow up would be done and then evaluated. To know the problem has been solved or not. Thus, it is a process and could be developed by practice.

Creativity

Creativity attracts the attention of experts and responsibilities so that they use it for their planning and working. Creativity has a relationship with academic achievement (Habibollah. Naderi, 2010). Surapuramath (2014) stated that creativity is a multidimensional phenomenon consisting of personality characteristics, cognitive methods, capacity, and motivation and related to academic achievement. And it has appeared in social relationships or individual. Kaboodi and Jiar (2012) say that it is a human mental capacity that helps to use their thinking and give opinions.

Thus, creativity is the heart of innovation, which helps the pupil teachers to apply their imagination, to develop ideas, questions, hypotheses, and experiments and evaluate them with own and peer groups ideas, products, and

processes. It generates the ideas, which have value to the individual, curiosity, motivation, confidence, and imagination which help to generate new product, rules, and regulation or we can say innovation.

Communication

Communication is a process that helps to express views, thoughts, and experiences to others. It has many ways like verbally, non-verbally, written, face to face communication, etc. Thus, it is a process of receiving and sending the information. Without communication, no one can achieve a goal, success, or anything.

Collaboration

Schrage (1995) states that collaboration is a group of value creation, as two or more individuals with complementary skills interacting to create a shared understanding that none had previously possessed or could have come to on their own. Schrage (1995) describes thirteen ingredients that influence collaboration those ingredients are related to human factors.

Collaboration is a way to work together to produce successful outcomes. In this, two or more people interact to complete a specific task. In this, people learn about social behaviour as they work together in the same situation and to achieve the same goal.

Academic achievement

It is the current position of a student's learning. In other words, academic achievement refers to what the student has learned or what skills the student has learned and is usually measured through assessments like standardized tests, performance assessments, and portfolio assessments. It refers to the level of schooling which is completed successfully and the ability to attain success in the studies by a student.

For academic achievement last appeared course marks of pupil teachers are considered.

Objectives

Main objective 1-: To explore the Innovative skills among pupil teachers.

Main objective 2-: To study the relationship between innovative skills and academic achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub-objective 2.1-: To study the relationship between Critical Thinking Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub-objective 2.2-: To study the relationship between Problem Solving Skill and Academic Achievement of

pupil teachers.

Sub-objective 2.3-: To study the relationship between Creativity Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub-objective 2.4-: To study the relationship between Communication Skill, and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub-objective 2.5-: To study the relationship between Collaboration Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Hypothesis

Main H0 1-: There is no significant relationship between Innovative skills and the Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub H0 1.1-: There is no significant relationship between Critical Thinking Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub H0 1.2-: There is no significant relationship between Problem Solving Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub H0 1.3-: There is no significant relationship between Creativity Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub H0 1.4-: There is no significant relationship between Communication Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub H0 1.5-: There is no significant relationship between Collaboration Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

One objective of Atal Innovation Mission is Innovation promotion to provide a platform where innovative ideas are generated. This mission was launched in 2016. This research will be helpful in this mission.

In the present scenario, we are depending on technology like the internet, Google, etc. day by day. If we want to do something usually, we take the help of technology, we never think of our effort or use our mind to do that work without the help of technology. In this way, individual creativity never comes out. So, explorations of innovative skills are required for the development.

For example: in daily life, if we do the same work, eat the same things, and wear the same dresses daily our life will be monotonous and there will be no development. For development, innovation, skills are required. So, exploration of innovative skills is the need of today.

We know very well that the progress of any country depends on the education of citizens. If our education will

not be innovation-based our country will not develop or progress. So, for the development of our country, exploration of innovative skills and the relationship between innovative skills and academic achievement is the need of the present scenario.

Methodology

Method of the study

Researchers have used various research strategies and methods to conduct a study such as historical, philosophical, case study, survey, experimental, ex-post-facto, etc. The most suitable method for a particular study is chosen and used. To find out the most appropriate method for this study, the researcher reviewed a number of research studies conducted so far and the **Descriptive Survey Method** was used for this study.

Population

All the pupil teachers studying in the institutes of Ghaziabad affiliated under CCSU were taken for this research.

Sample and sampling technique

A sample of 45 pupil teachers was selected from B.Ed. of Ghaziabad institute affiliated under CCS University for the research through **Random Cluster Sampling Technique**.

First, the researcher prepared a list of all institutes of Ghaziabad affiliated under CCS University and 3 institutes were selected through **Random Lottery Method**. A cluster of 15 pupil teachers was taken randomly from one institute. Thus, 45 pupil teachers were selected from 3 institutes of Ghaziabad affiliated under CCS University.

Tools

Five rating scales on the innovative skills were constructed by the researcher and critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration skills were calculated of pupil teachers.

To check the critical thinking skills student's perceptions, assumptions, emotions, logic, and implications and consequences were measured. To check problem-solving skills pupil teachers' problem identification, explanation, brainstorm ideas, solution regarding problems, implementation of the selected solution, and evaluation were measured. To check creativity, the novelty of ideas, motivation, confidence, curiosity, and imagination was measured. To check communication skills, clarity of message, use of appropriate sources, active listening, asking questions, observing non-verbal actions or reactions, and speed and sequence of communication were measured. To check collaboration skills, participation, trust, and common mission, appreciating group members, accountability, and time management were measured. Thus, innovative skills were measured with

B.Ed. First-year pupil teachers.

Content cum face validity was calculated for validation of experts based on the five-rating scale. The Percentage of agreeability of every item was calculated and 95-100% agreeability items were accepted.

For the reliability of the innovative skills scale, Cronbach's Alpha was calculated on Microsoft Excel. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure internal consistency which means how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is a measure of scale reliability. Cronbach's Alpha was 0.871. The general rule of thumb about Cronbach's Alpha is that 0.70 and above is good, 0.80 and above is better and 0.90 and above is best. In this way, the reliability of this questionnaire is better.

Data were collected from 45 B.Ed. Pupil teachers with the help of an innovative skills questionnaire. To check the relationship between innovative skills and academic achievements the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation was used. With the help of the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation expresses the extent to which changes in one variable are accompanied by or dependent upon changes in a second variable.

Statistical analysis

To find out the relationship between the two groups 'The Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation' was calculated to express the extent to which changes in one variable are accompanied by or dependent upon changes in a second variable.

Results

The hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between Innovative skills and the Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

Sub hypothesis-1 states that there is no significant relationship between Critical Thinking Skills and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

After applying the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation between Critical thinking skills and academic achievement the correlation was 0.92 which is more than the table value at 0.05 (0.304) and 0.01 (0.393) levels of significance. So, the null hypothesis was rejected at both levels and concluded that there is a very high positive correlation between critical thinking skills and academic achievement.

Sub hypothesis-2 states that there is no significant relationship between Problem Solving Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

After applying the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation between problem-solving skills and academic achievement the correlation was 0.65 which is more than the table value at 0.05 (0.304) and 0.01 (0.393) levels

of significance. So, the null hypothesis was rejected at both levels and concluded that there is a moderate positive correlation between problem-solving skills and academic achievement.

Sub hypothesis-3 states that there is no significant relationship between Creativity Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

After applying the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation between creativity skills and academic achievement the correlation was 0.39 which is more than the table value at 0.05 (0.304) level of significance and less than the table value at 0.01 (0.393) level of significance. So, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 levels and concluded that there is a low positive correlation between creativity skills and academic achievement.

Sub hypothesis-4 states that there is no significant relationship between Communication Skills and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

After applying the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation between communication skills and academic achievement the correlation was 0.84 which is more than the table value at 0.05 (0.304) and 0.01 (0.393) levels of significance. So, the null hypothesis was rejected at both levels and concluded that there is a high positive correlation between communication skills and academic achievement.

Sub hypothesis-5 states that there is no significant relationship between Collaboration Skill and Academic Achievement of pupil teachers.

After applying the Product-Moment Coefficient of correlation between collaboration skills and academic achievement the correlation was 0.69 which is more than the table value at 0.05 (0.304) and 0.01 (0.393) levels of significance. So, the null hypothesis was rejected at both levels and concluded that there is a moderate positive correlation between collaboration skills and academic achievement.

Discussion

Innovation is required to develop the country. Our country India is a developing country. So, innovation is a big requirement for our country India to be a developed country. Innovation in every field is the demand of the present scenario. Innovation cannot be happening without innovative skills. Innovative skills are the basic requirement of innovative skills.

Education is the engine, or we can say a powerful weapon for the development of any country. To educate every person teacher are required. To inculcate innovative skills in students, teachers should have innovative skills so innovative skills were explored among pupil teachers. And calculate the relationship between innovative skills and academic achievement. Innovative skills are the set of skills that help a person in innovation. Critical thinking, Problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration skills are included in innovative skills.

Critical thinking is must go ahead. For critical thinking, perception, assumptions, emotions, logic, and implications, and consequences are required. Without perception, assumptions, emotions, logic and implications, and consequences we cannot go ahead or cannot get success. We can say that to think positively in daily life and to get success critical thinking is required.

Problem-solving is a process in which a person first identifies the problems based on the thinking level, then explain and present that how to be saved and after this planned to solve the problem and collected the information. According to prioritize resources would be selected and used. Then the follow-up would be done and then evaluated, to know the problem has been solved or not. Thus, it is a process and could be developed by practice. These problem-solving skills are also required for the development of the country. In our country, India there are many problems. To solve the problem, problem-solving skills are required in the present scenario to be a developed country.

Creativity is the heart of innovation. Without creativity, innovation cannot be possible. It helps to apply their imagination, to develop ideas, questions, hypotheses, and experiments, and evaluate them with own and peer, groups, ideas, products, and processes. It generates the ideas, which have value to the individual, curiosity, motivation, confidence, and imagination which help to generate new product, rules, and regulation or we can say innovation. Thus, the novelty of ideas, motivation, confidence, curiosity, and imagination should be with a person for creativity.

Communication is a process that helps to express views, thoughts, and experiences to others. It has many ways like verbally, non-verbally, written, face to face communication, etc. Thus, it is a process of receiving and sending the information. Without communication, no one can achieve a goal, success, or anything. Clarity of message, use of appropriate sources, active listening, asking questions, observing non-verbal actions or reactions, and speed and sequence of communication are important for innovation.

Collaboration is a way to work together to produce successful outcomes. In this, two or more people interact to complete a specific task. In this, a person learns about social behaviour as they work together in the same situation and to achieve the same goal. So, participation, trust, a common mission, appreciating group members, accountability, and time management are important for collaboration.

If we talk about academic achievement, it is the current position of a student's learning. It refers to the level of schooling which is completed successfully and the ability to attain success in the studies by a student. Academic achievement is a source to check the level of a person's achievement.

Conclusion

In the present scenario innovation is necessary for development in every field. So, innovative skills should be inculcated in everyone as without innovative skills innovation cannot be possible. In innovative skills, critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration skills are included because without critical thinking no one can observe or understand others and cannot be successful to solve the problem and to solve problem creativity is necessary and without communication, it cannot be possible and for communication, collaboration should be there. Thus, all skills are interrelated without anyone innovation cannot be possible. Innovative skills are positively correlated with achievement. It means if a person is skilful in critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration his or her achievements will be high.

Educational implications

FOR ADMINISTRATORS AND SUPERVISORS

- The principal should maintain the proper working environment in the school for better innovation.
- The supervisor should encourage good suggestions from senior teachers because skill increases with time.
- At the time of requirement, the fact of innovative skills should be considered.

FOR POLICYMAKERS

- The policymaker should arrange all the essential activities to enhance innovative skills.
- They should make provisions to enhance skills like arranging seminars and in-service programs for all the teachers free of cost.
- Studies stated earlier imply that skills can be enhanced, cultivated through training. Hence the training modules for teachers at all levels must include a component of enhancing their innovative skills.

FOR TEACHERS

Unless the teachers themselves will not realize their conditions, and it is because they would not be able to improve them. For this teacher should consider the following points-:

- They must give them more time to understand their pupil teachers.
- They must maintain a friendly environment at the time of teaching.
- They must try to enhance their innovative skills.

Not only in education, but innovative skills are also the requirement of every field like medical, corporate, industrial, agriculture, production, etc. So, to make our country India a developed country it is necessary to inculcate innovative skills in every student.

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